

TABLE 4—TGA DATA OF COMPLEXES

Temp. °C	% Weight loss of pigment containing			
	Mn(II)	Fe(II)	Zn(II)	Cd(II)
100	0.19	...	7.10	4.94
120	0.65	...	8.68	5.35
160	1.57	...	10.52	8.65
200	2.68	...	13.15	9.67
240	4.79	...	14.73	12.92
280	8.63	15.87	17.89	16.06
300	12.86	20.87	21.02	18.27
320	20.92	22.22	23.68	22.58
340	24.76	25.00	25.52	24.88
360	26.10	29.16	27.63	26.23
380	27.44	32.40	28.94	27.89
400	28.21	32.40	30.26	29.45
500	33.20	41.60	56.57	47.81
600	41.91	48.14	85.52	61.72
700	47.79	56.94	86.02	78.49
800	53.74	58.33	85.52	78.49
900	60.07	...	...	78.49

weight loss at temperatures lower than this range lies between 20–26%. The order of thermal stability is Cd(380°) > Mn(320°) > Fe(300°) ~ Zn(300°). The weights of the residues do not conform to those of the metal oxides.

The insolubility of the pigments, composition, ir spectra and thermal stability are evidences of their polymeric structure, as given below.

M = Mn(II), Fe(II), Zn(II), Cd(II);
n = degree of polymerization.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Zinc(II)

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DIVALENT zinc ion has completely filled $3d^{10}$ non-bonding shell and hence usually forms four coordinated tetrahedral compounds utilizing $4s4p^3$ hybrid orbitals for bonding. If experimental conditions are favourable, the coordination number can be increased to five involving one $4d$ orbital¹⁻³. This communication describes the mixed ligand complexes of the type $M[Zn(\beta\text{-dik})_2L]$ and $Zn(\beta\text{-dik})_2L'$ where $M = K^+$, Na^+ or Me_4N^+ ; $\beta\text{-dik}$ = acetylacetonate or dibenzoylmethanate; $L = SCN^-$, N_3^- or CN^- and L' = imidazole, morpholine and their derivatives.

Experimental

The β -diketonates of Zn(II) were prepared by the usual method⁴. Their thiocyanate, cyanide and azide adducts were obtained by refluxing the solutions of β -diketonates of Zn(II) in methanol with methanolic solutions of potassium thiocyanate, cyanide or sodium azide in 1 : 1 molar ratio for 2 to 3 hr. The mixed ligand complexes separated out on cooling. The compound $K[Zn(bz bz)_2(SCN)]$ so formed was treated with tetramethyl ammonium chloride in methanol. The precipitated potassium chloride was filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated to get the mixed ligand complex $Me_4N[Zn(bz bz)_2(SCN)]$. The complexes of the type $Zn(\beta\text{-dik})_2L'$ were prepared by refluxing Zn(II) acetylacetonate with imidazole, morpholine and their derivatives in methanol for 30 min to 2 hr. Morpholine and 2-methyl imidazole adducts separated out after keeping the solution overnight whereas other compounds separated out after 3 days. All the compounds were suction filtered, washed several times with ethanol to ensure complete removal of the excess ligand, followed by other and dried *in vacuo*.

The composition of the complexes was established by estimating zinc as $ZnNH_4PO_4$, sulphur as $BaSO_4$ after oxidizing with bromine in carbontetrachloride solution and nitrogen by Kjeldahl method⁵. The conductance measurements were carried out with $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solutions in acetone, pyridine and methanol medium using Toshniwal conductivity bridge and a dip type cell. The infrared absorption spectra were recorded on Nujol mull using Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. The physical, analytical, conductance and infrared spectral data are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Results and Discussion

For the compounds of the type $M[Zn(\beta\text{-dik})_2L]$, the molar conductance data indicate them to be

NOTES

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Compound	Colour	m.p. °C	Zn% Found (Calcd.)	S% Found (Calcd.)	N% Found (Calcd.)	Δm mhos (medium)
1.	$K[Zn(acac)_2(SCN)]$	White	>250	18.0 (18.1)	9.1 (8.8)	—	155 (acetone)
2.	$Na[Zn(acac)_2(N_3)]$	White	>250	20.0 (19.9)	—	—	66 (pyridine)
3.	$Me_2N[Zn(bz bz)_2(SCN)]$	Light orange	165	10.0 (10.1)	5.1 (4.9)	—	162 (acetone)
4.	$Na[Zn(bz bz)_2(N_3)]$	Yellowish white	>250	11.8 (11.9)	—	—	62 (pyridine)
5.	$K[Zn(acac)_2(ON)]$	White	>250	19.8 (19.9)	—	—	154 (acetone)
6.	$K[Zn(bz bz)_2(CN)]$	Light orange	>250	11.2 (11.3)	—	—	127 (methanol)
7.	$Zn(acac)_2(moph)$	White	223	18.3 (18.6)	—	4.0 (3.9)	18.2 (pyridine)
8.	$Zn(acac)_2(I.Z.)$	Pinkish white	135	19.6 (19.7)	—	4.0 (4.2)	24.5 (pyridine)
9.	$Zn(acac)_2(2Me.I.Z.)$	Light yellow	90	18.8 (18.9)	—	3.9 (4.0)	26.0 (pyridine)
10.	$Zn(acac)_2(B.I.Z.)$	White	>250	16.4 (16.9)	—	3.2 (3.4)	27.3 (pyridine)
11.	$Zn(acac)_2(2Me.B.I.Z.)$	White	215	15.6 (15.5)	—	3.3 (3.3)	25.4 (pyridine)

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA IN cm^{-1}

Sl. No.	Compounds	β -diketone		Thiocyanate or cyanide		Azide			
		$\nu(C-C)$	$\nu(C-O)$	$\nu(C-N)$	$\nu(C-S)$	ν_{asym}	ν_{sym}	$\nu(N-H)$	$\nu(N-H)$
1.	$K[Zn(acac)_2(SCN)]$	1600s	1520s	2035vs	715s	—	—	—	—
2.	$Na[Zn(acac)_2(N_3)]$	1605s	1525s	—	—	2080s	1260s	—	—
3.	$Me_2N[Zn(bz bz)_2(SCN)]$	1605vs	1530vs	2060vs	710s	—	—	—	—
4.	$Na[Zn(bz bz)_2(N_3)]$	1600s	1535s	—	—	2040s	1275s	—	—
5.	$K[Zn(acac)_2(ON)]$	1600s	1520s	2040m	—	—	—	—	—
6.	$K[Zn(bz bz)_2(ON)]$	1605s	1525s	2055m	—	—	—	—	—
7.	$Zn(acac)_2(moph)$	1605vs	1550vs	—	—	—	—	1425m	3255m
8.	$Zn(acac)_2(I.Z.)$	1613s	1555s	—	—	—	—	1423m	3350m
9.	$Zn(acac)_2(2Me.I.Z.)$	1610vs	1530vs	—	—	—	—	1440sh	3270m
10.	$Zn(acac)_2(B.I.Z.)$	1605s	1525s	—	—	—	—	1430m	3300m
11.	$Zn(acac)_2(2Me.B.I.Z.)$	1596vs	1520vs	—	—	—	—	1413sh	3360m

s = sharp

vs = very sharp

m = medium

sh = shoulder

1:1 electrolytes. The absorption due to $\nu(C-C)$ and $\nu(C-O)$ are shifted to lower frequencies due to metal ligand π -linkage superimposed on $L \rightarrow M$ σ bond⁸. $\nu(C-N)$ bands appear at 2030 and 2060 cm^{-1} and $\nu(C-S)$ appears at ~ 715 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of terminal S-bonded thiocyanate group⁷. The ionic KN_3 absorbs at 2042 cm^{-1} (ν_{asym}) and 1344 cm^{-1} (ν_{sym})⁸. In the compounds under report, the strong bands observed for ν_{sym} and ν_{asym} are in accordance with the earlier observations^{9,10}.

For complexes of the type $Zn(\beta-dik)_2L'$, the molar conductance data indicate them to be non-electrolytic. The $\nu(M-O)$ of $Zn(acac)_2$ is shifted to lower frequencies upon adduct formation showing direct coordination of donor molecule with the metal ions. The absence of absorption bands at 3490 cm^{-1} due to coordinated water and the presence of absorption bands¹¹ at ~ 1430 and ~ 3300 cm^{-1} due to (N-H) bending and stretching

frequencies clearly indicate the presence of N-donor ligands which have replaced the coordinated water from the parent compound. The compounds No. 3, 4, 6, 8, 9 exhibit light colours due to presence of the mixed ligands like other complexes^{12,13} of $Zn(II)$ and $Cd(II)$. Hence all the complexes are presumed to be penta coordinated.

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Studies of ESR Spectra of Some Cu(II) Complexes

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THE esr spectra of copper(II) complexes have been studied by many workers¹⁻⁸. Some of these studies have led to useful conclusion regarding the stereochemistry of Cu(II) in these complexes and the nature of metal-ligand bonding. Detailed esr studies on Cu(II) ion, bonded to oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur atom of the ligand, have been reported^{9,10}. The authors have studied the metal-ligand bond strengths using esr data and the findings are presented here.

Materials and methods :

The copper(II) complexes studied in the present investigation are (i) Cu(HMMCO)₂.3H₂O and

Cu(HBMMCO)₂.3H₂O (HMMCO = 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone oxime, HBMMCO = 2'-hydroxy - 3' - bromo-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone oxime); (ii) Cu(TMBHA)₂.3H₂O (TMBHA = N-m-tolyl-p-methoxy benzohydroxamic acid) and Cu(BPPTB)₂.2H₂O (BPPTB = 4-S-benzyl-1-p-Cl-phenyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret). These complexes were prepared by the methods described earlier²¹⁻²⁴. Electronic spectra, magnetic measurement, conductivity etc. suggest tetragonal symmetry to these complexes²¹⁻²⁴.

The esr spectra of copper(II) complexes of HMMCO and BPPTB were taken at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature in chloroform solution (Fig. 1). ESR spectra of copper(II) complexes of HMMCO, HBMMCO, TMBHA and BPPTB were taken in polycrystalline state at room temperature only (Fig. 2).

The esr spectra of the same copper complexes at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature were obtained from the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, I.I.T., Madras. The esr spectra of some copper complexes at room temperature were also run for us by the E.S.R. Laboratory, I.I.T., Bombay.

Results and Discussion

The esr spectra were analysed by the method of Kneubuhl²⁵, Sands²⁶ and Garman *et al.*¹⁴. The g values at room temperature are presented in Table 1 and the hyperfine coupling constants and g values at liquid nitrogen temperature are shown in Table 2. The nature of esr spectrum (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2) of copper(II) complexes in the present study

Fig. 1